

ISic3621

I.Sicily inscription 3621

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

natural rock

Object

painted rock face

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Melita

Place of origin (modern)

Malta

Provenance

Rabat, catacomb of the rupestral church of St. Agata, wall

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Rabat, in situ

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645694

EDCS 59500345

Bibliography

1888-. *L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 2010.0614

1923-. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 59.1082

Rizzone, V.G. 2009. Iscrizioni giudaica e cristiane di Malta. *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik*. 168: 202-208. At 203-204 no.2 ph

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3621. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388845>